

**Machine Learning Workshop: “New Opportunities in
ML/AI for Weather and Climate Modelling”
- A virtual workshop held jointly with IS-ENES3**

Deliverable D2.10

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About this document

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1. Abstract /publishable summary

This report describes the virtual workshop entitled “New Opportunities for ML/AI in Weather and Climate Modelling” held over the three days of 16-18 March 2021.

The aim of the workshop was to bring together climate scientists and experts from academia and industry to share knowledge and experience and to identify new opportunities in the areas of machine learning, artificial intelligence and big data techniques for Weather and Climate Modelling. A total of 21 talks, distributed in three sessions centred on complementary aspects of ML/AI, were given during the workshop by scientists/experts from academia, research centres and industry around the world. Due to the COVID pandemic, the workshop was organized as a virtual event and attended by a large audience with 206 participants - out of 287 registered participants - joining.

The workshop was sponsored jointly by the IS-ENES3 project and the ESiWACE2 Centre of Excellence. Each project had complimentary interests in the workshop. ESiWACE2 essentially having a focus *inward* to the Weather and Climate modelling community while the focus of IS-ENES3 is more *outwards* toward other communities and industrial partners. The workshop was an opportunity to generate synergies between the two projects and helped to bring the two communities of Earth System model development at extreme scale and the Climate modelling community closer together.

2. Conclusion & Results

The workshop was organized around three three-and-a-half hour sessions, each commencing at 3pm CET:

- (Day 1): Views from Domain Science
- (Day 2): ML/AI Software Technologies
- (Day 3): High performance, Infrastructure and Big data Challenges

The first session, “Views from Domain Science” is particularly relevant to the ESiWACE2 Centre of Excellence community and this document focuses on presenting contributions from the workshop relevant to specific scientific topics in the Weather and Climate modelling community. Days 2 and 3 should be of particular interest to the more general Weather and Climate community; therefore, IS-ENES3 Milestone Report MS16, “New Technical Opportunities workshop in ML and AI”, provides an overview of the talks presented at the workshop. Aspects of ML/AI relevant to the IS-ENES3 project are also explored in sections of IS-ENES3 deliverable, D4.5, “White Paper on Innovation, Tools, Platforms and Techniques”.

The workshop website can be viewed at:

[Joint IS-ENES3/ESiWACE2 Virtual Workshop on New Opportunities for ML and AI in Weather and Climate Modelling](#)

The website provides links to the workshop agenda as well as links to the presentations and videos of the talks presented in each session.

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The following IS-ENES3 link is to google docs (“IS-ENES3/ESiWACE ML/AI in Weather and Climate modelling workshop – March 2021”) where the documents related to the workshop (including links to the Q&A documents of each session and copies of the presentations) can be found: https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1XtxoxO4zbuAizG7Uw9clw4Gd_0yK1B0L

The Q&A documents associated with each session summarize the discussions following each talk; these documents provide a further useful resource to the community. The use of Q&A documents proved to be effective in fostering the discussion among presenters and participants in the virtual workshop and to reduce the need to discuss all questions in plenary while time is limited.

3. Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to the achievement of all the macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the Description of the Action:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable?
(1) Enable leading European weather and climate models to leverage the available performance of pre-exascale systems with regard to both compute and data capacity in 2021.	
(2) Prepare the weather and climate community to be able to make use of exascale systems when they become available.	x

Specific goals in the workplan	Contribution of this deliverable?
Boost European climate and weather models to operate in world-leading quality on existing supercomputing and future pre-exascale platforms	x
Establish new technologies for weather and climate modelling	x
Enhance HPC capacity of the weather and climate community	
Improve the toolchain to manage data from climate and weather simulations at scale	x
Strengthen the interaction with the European HPC ecosystem	x
Foster co-design between model developers, HPC manufacturers and HPC centres	

4. Detailed report on the deliverable

This section presents first an overview of the organization of the workshop and provides links to the outputs from the workshop. Following this, a summary listing of the talks in each session is presented. The final section, rather than summarizing each specific talk in turn, provides a commentary on the presentations along scientific topic lines of interest to the Weather and Climate community.

OVERVIEW

The workshop was organized around three three-and-a-half hour sessions, each commencing at 3pm CET on consecutive days:

- Day 1: Views from Domain Science
- Day 2: ML/AI Software Technologies
- Day 3: High performance, Infrastructure and Big data Challenges

The workshop sessions on each day were structured with seven talks and a panel session. The first talk was a 40-minute keynote that included an introduction into the topic, with the other six talks being 20 minutes each, including questions. The panel sessions lasted approximately half-an-hour. The complete workshop agenda is enclosed at the end of this document (Annex 1).

The organizing committee consisted of:

- (Chair) Graham Riley (University of Manchester, UK)
- (Co-chair) Giovanni Aloisio (CMCC, University of Salento, Italy)
- Jean-Claude Andre (France)
- (Session 2 chair) Caroline Arnold (DKRZ, Germany)
- V. Balaji (Princeton, USA)
- Peter Dueben (ECMWF, UK)
- (Session 1 chair) Marlene Kretschmer (University of Reading, UK)
- (Session 3 chair) Carlos Gomez Gonzalez (BSc, Spain)
- Donatello Elia (CMCC, University of Salento, Italy)

Of the total of 21 speakers, 14 were from academic institutions and Weather and Climate centres around the world and 7 were from industry, representing both software and hardware technology developers as well as service providers. In particular, the speakers from industry were:

- Luke Madaus & Steve Sain from Jupiter Intelligence,
- Stephan Rasp from ClimateAI,
- Akshay Subramaniam and Thorsten Kurth representing two parts of NVIDIA,
- Pete Warden from Google,
- Phil Ridley from Arm,
- Jonathan Weyn from Microsoft Research/U. of Washington.

Among speakers, 17.4% identified themselves as female and 82.6% as male. Of those who answered the question on their career stage, 14% were PhD students, 19% engineers, 24% postdocs and 43% identified as researchers.

The workshop was very well attended. During the workshop there was a total of 206 unique participants taking part in the three sessions (out of a total of 287 registrations). These were spread over the three sessions as follows: Day 1: 173 participants, Day 2: 136 participants, Day 3: 97 participants.

The participants had a range of backgrounds from across academia, weather and climate centres and industry around the world. There were representatives from the following companies registered for the workshop: Ramboll, Arm, Google, Cervest Ltd., Wikilimo, NVIDIA Ltd., Predictia Intelligent Data, SISTMMA GmbH, ARCADIS, Airbus, Benchmark Labs, Climate Scale, Descartes Labs, Lobelia Earth, CIEMET, Randbee Consultants, Eötvös Loránd, ClimateAI, ClimaCell, NUS, Kyrgyzhydromet, Arpaee, Verisk Maplecroft, Simula, Jupiter Intelligence, Microsoft.

Among the regular participants who were not speakers, 29.8% identified themselves as female, 65.9% as male and 4.3% preferred not to declare. Of those who answered the question on their career stage, 13% were engineers, 18% postdocs, 24% PhD students and 45% identified as researchers.

LIST OF TALKS

(Day 1): Views from Domain Science

- Emily Shuckburgh (University of Cambridge): *New approaches based on ML for a range of climate prediction problems.*
- Luke Madaus & Steve Sain (Jupiter Intelligence): *Philosophy and Targeted Applications of ML/AI Techniques for Climate Risk Analytics at Jupiter.*
- Stephan Rasp (ClimateAI): *The optimization dichotomy: Why is it so hard to improve climate models with machine learning.*
- Zhaoyi Shen (Caltech): *Improving convection parameterizations with a library of large-eddy simulations.*
- Rachel Prudden (MetOffice Informatics Lab): *Stochastic Super-Resolution for Convective Regimes using Gaussian Random Fields.*
- Kirsten Mayer (Colorado State University): *Subseasonal Forecasts of Opportunity Identified by an Explainable Neural Network.*
- Pedram Hassanzadeh (Rice University): *Using transfer learning and backscattering analysis to build stable, generalizable data-driven subgrid-scale models: A 2D turbulence test case.*

(Day 2): ML/AI Software Technologies

- Jussi Leinonen (MeteoSwiss): *Stochastic machine learning for atmospheric fields with generative adversarial networks.*
- Andreas Gerhardus (DLR Jena): *Causal discovery in time series with unobserved confounders.*
- Jinlong Wu (Caltech): *Estimating stochastic closures using sparsity-promoting ensemble Kalman inversion.*

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- Gionata Ghiggi and Michaël Defferrard (EPFL): *Deep Learning on the sphere for weather/climate applications.*
- Thomas Chen (AMSE): *Deep learning-based remote sensing for infrastructure damage assessment.*
- Akshay Subramaniam (NVIDIA): *Leveraging physics information in neural networks for fluid flow problems.*
- Jonathan Weyn (Microsoft Research/University of Washington): *Sub-seasonal forecasting with a large ensemble of deep-learning weather prediction models.*

(Day 3): High performance, Infrastructure and Big data Challenges

- Tal Ben-Nun (ETHZ): *Scaling Up Deep Learning Workloads - A Data-Centric View.*
- Micheal Simpson (NOAA): *Radar QPE and Machine Learning.*
- Pete Warden (Google): *Using ML at the Edge to Improve Data Gathering.*
- Phil Ridley (Arm Ltd.): *An Overview of ML and AI on Arm Based HPC Systems for Weather and Climate Applications.*
- Jan Ackmann (Oxford University): *Machine-Learned Preconditioners for Linear Solvers in Geophysical Fluid Flows.*
- Theo McCaie (MetOffice Informatics Lab): *You do you. How next-gen data platforms can stop weather and climate scientists from being software engineers and other perversions.*
- Torsten Kurth (NVIDIA): *3D bias correction with deep learning in the Integrated Forecasting System.*

SCIENTIFIC TOPIC-BASED COMMENTARY

This section provides an overview with a particular focus on the scientific topics of the talks in the first two sessions. Aspects of the underlying software technologies presented mainly in sessions 2 and 3 are further discussed in the IS-ENES3 Milestone Report MS16, “New Technical Opportunities workshop in ML and AI” and IS-ENES3 deliverable, D4.5. The Q&A documents associated with the sessions are also useful sources of further information.

Session 1: Views from Domain Science

In the keynote talk of the session on day 1, “Views from Domain Science”, *Emily Shuckburgh (University of Cambridge)* discussed the exploration of data-driven models in the following four application areas:

- **Sea ice forecasting:** Using data driven techniques to forecast seasonal arctic ice more accurately. This involved representing satellite data and other Met data as 2D images which could be passed to a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) and performing a classification task to identify three categories of sea ice cover: open water ($\leq 15\%$ ice); marginal; full sea ice ($\geq 80\%$). Training was performed on the CMIP6 database and observational data. The *skill* of the model was found to be above that of the current, traditional physics-based models.

- **Heatwave prediction:** The idea was to use historical information to bias-correct existing physical models by learning a correction from data using a Gaussian Process (GP) approach. The indications are that this approach can work better than existing methods.
- **Ocean Modelling:** In this example, the aim was to try to understand the physical basis of the Data-driven model developed – exploring an approach to *interpretability*. Again, the model showed reasonable skill.
- **Hydrological Flooding:** The fourth example was in the area of climate impact modelling and explored another use of data-driven models, in this case seeking to find a data-driven model of the damage function of flooding. This work was somewhat preliminary but suggests that data-driven models have wide applicability.

There were several talks addressing the topic of **uncertainty in climate predictions arising from sub-gridscale parameterizations** with emphasis on **cloud and turbulence modelling**. *Stephan Rasp (ClimateAI)* discussed one approach based on replacing physics models by ML-based emulators trained from model data, which can typically execute much faster. However, it is difficult to develop suitable coarse-grained datasets from conventional high-resolution models. In the case of, for example, radiation and gravity wave models, there exist good parameterizations already, and these can be used to provide (good) training data for emulators. Optimising tendencies appears to be the best approach based on recent literature. However, generally, there still appears to be no obvious, general method to optimize for time-step sub-grid tendencies, and Neural Nets (NNs) can interpolate but not extrapolate successfully outside of the domain of their training sets, so using model data to train has severe limitations. Ideally, emulators would be trained in a more realistic, coupled model (online) rather than outside (offline) in the context of only the input domain range for the radiation model, for example. Stephan pointed out that lots of climate datasets are now emerging, for example, at mldata.pangeo.io. Stephan also pointed out that there is the possibility of applying evolutionary models rather than NNs to this type of problem.

On the same topic, *Zhaoyi Shen (Caltech)* discussed an approach to **improving convection parameterizations based on the development of a library of large-eddy simulations (LES)**, focussing on LES of turbulence, clouds, and convection in the context of global climate models (GCMs), where much of the uncertainty in climate models is due to the modelling of low-level clouds. Zhaoyi presented a framework in which LES are driven by large-scale forcings from a GCM in order to create a library of LES of clouds across a range of dynamical regimes. Such a library can be used to provide training sets to improve GCM parameterizations using data assimilation techniques and ML techniques. The talk presented some early results on the successful calibration of convective parameterizations using the library.

A third talk on this topic was that of *Rachel Prudden (MetOffice Informatics Lab)*. The talk focussed on **convection**, the simulation of which is currently at the edge of current resolutions. The approach is to treat downscaling (which is an ill-posed problem) as a statistical problem. Rather than training a NN, the idea is to use an approach **based on Gaussian Random Fields** (i.e., a Gaussian Process with 2D fields). These models require hardly any training and so are much cheaper than training NNs. A stochastic, generative method is required since convective-scale weather has a high degree of independence from larger scales (ill-posed). The approach was illustrated with an application to wet

bulb potential temperature (WBPT) data over the UK. It is early days, but the approach seems promising.

A final talk in this space was given by *Pedram Hassanzaheh (Rice University)* and focussed on a new technique developed in the context of **turbulence modelling** using a 2D turbulence test case. The talk focused on techniques to learn tricky parameterization terms in the equation linking low-level turbulence (requiring a very high-resolution grid and very small timesteps) to LES models (on coarse grids, around 1/8 of the size, and using a longer timestep, around x10 larger). The idea is to use Data-driven parameterization (DD-P) to learn (represent) the tricky terms in the LES equation. The use of CNNs and Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) has been explored. However, there is an issue that physics-based models do diffusion well but not back-scattering and the current DD-P models do not generalize (extrapolate) well to high Reynolds number (Re) flows. Hence Transfer Learning has been used, where a DNN has fixed layers trained with low Re data but has a number of layers re-trained with high Re data. An extension using, in addition, an Auto-Encoder allows both transfer learning to high Re and coarser grids, which is showing promise.

Kirsten Mayer (Colorado State University) described work on **sub-seasonal forecasting**. There are occasions when the atmospheric conditions are favourable to prediction which can lead to enhanced skill in forecasting; these are known as “forecasts of opportunity”. Kirsten described an example prediction related to the Madden-Julia Oscillation (MJO) concerning sub-seasonal (2 weeks to 2 months) prediction in midlatitudes which is difficult due to the chaotic nature of the atmosphere. The idea is to use NNs to classify (using SoftMax activation functions) the confidence in predictions of positive or negative circulation in MJO in the tropics at a location two weeks into the future. High confidence from the NN would imply higher accuracy in the prediction. Kirsten went on discussing a technique to extract from the NN, by backpropagating output through the network, physical features of the MJO at prediction time which could be related to the known categories of MJO and support explanation of the observed behaviour. For example, a positive prediction of circulation is seen to be associated with enhanced and suppressed convection regions. Using this technique, Layer-wise Relevance Propagation (LRP) maps can be generated, and clustering techniques can help identify these forecasts of opportunity and provide evidence (**explainability**) for why the network had an accurate prediction.

Luke Madaus (Jupiter Intel) emphasized some of the issues related to the *interpretability* (i.e., **explainability** and the transparency) of results using ML techniques from both their own science teams at Jupiter Intl as well as from customers and other users of their data. Such clients have issues related to the validation of the tools used to generate predictions.

Session 2: ML/AI Software Technologies

In the second session, on day 2, “ML/AI Software Technologies”, *Jussi Leinonen (MeteoSwiss)*, in his keynote first gave an overview of the development of data-centric modelling from basic Neural Networks through CNNs and Encoder-Decoder architectures, followed by extensions which lead to Autoencoders and then to Residual Networks and Recurrent Nets and, finally, the development of Generative models and Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs). He then went on to describe an emerging **technology to manage uncertainty** in predictions based on the use of Conditional Generative Adversarial Networks (CGANs). Two examples were presented: the first being that of

generating vertical cloud profiles from MODIS spectrometer data and the second addressing **stochastic downscaling of precipitation data**.

Andreas Gerhardus (DLR Jena) described work on **Causal Discovery**, providing a mathematical basis for understanding cause and effect applied to Earth's complex climate system. Causal understanding can lead to physical insight (scientific understanding), to robust prediction and forecasting and also supports attribution ("Why did this happen?", "Is this due to climate change?"). An algorithm called LPCMCI is in development and has been applied to learning the cause-and-effect relationships in multivariate time series, which are a common form of climate data, showing promising results.

Jinlong Wu (Caltech) presented a novel approach to **producing better parameterizations ("closure models")**. Jinlong described a new technique to quantify model error in the closures of dynamical systems, such as turbulence models, for which current parameterizations are expensive to compute, based on Ensemble Kalman Inversion (EKI). He demonstrated the merit of introducing stochastic processes to quantify model error for certain systems. The topic of replacing existing closures with purely data-driven closures (i.e., emulators) using the proposed methodology was also discussed.

Gionata Ghiggi (EPFL) described the work that he and *Michael Defferrard* have done using Deep Learning (DL) to reduce the computation time when performing deep learning on unstructured grids. The work described a new technique for computing convolution and pooling operations, common in DL solutions, directly on several common grids defined on the sphere that are used in climate modelling: e.g., Gauss-Legendre, icosahedral, cubed-sphere. This technique allows overcoming problems the DL methods encounter on planar projections due to the non-uniform area of grid cells. Gionata believes the technique should be applicable to several areas, including, for example: **post-processing** (e.g., bias correction and downscaling), **model error corrections**, **linear solver preconditioning**, model components **emulation** and **sub-grid parametrizations**.

Thomas Chen (AMSE) presented a number of case studies applying **DL to rapidly assess damage** caused by extreme weather events and natural disasters. The importance of ML models interpretability was also addressed in this talk.

Akshay Subramaniam (NVIDIA) discussed new approaches in the area of physics-informed Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) applied to two areas of **fluid flow problems**. He first discussed an alternative approach (TEGAN) to the problem of modelling **turbulence** in the context of Large Eddy Simulation (LES) targeting the recovery of a high-resolution, point-based picture from a low resolution LES. The second part of the talk focussed on a technology to learn solutions of Partial Differential Equations (PDEs) with Physics-informed Neural Nets (PiNNs) using only the governing equations and given some boundary conditions, i.e., *without any data*. The technology is available in the NVIDIA SimNet toolkit.

Jonathan Weyn (Microsoft Research/University of Washington) described his work using large ensembles of DL weather prediction models with a focus on whether **CNNs** can be used to **predict the evolution of the whole atmosphere**. The system developed is called Deep Learning Weather Prediction (DLWP) and currently handles only a few (but key) variables and uses a cubed-sphere grid with the aim of predicting at a two-to-six-week timescale (i.e., **sub-seasonal to seasonal forecasts**).

Session 3: High performance, Infrastructure and Big data challenges

This subsection gives, for completion, a brief summary of the talks on the third session on day 3, “High performance, Infrastructure and Big data Challenges”. These talks relate to HPC, large-scale infrastructure and the challenges of Big data analytics processing. Further details of these talks can be found in the IS-ENES3 Milestone Report MS16, “New Technical Opportunities workshop in ML and AI”.

Tal Ben-Nun (ETHZ) discussed, in this keynote, the development of DNN compilers to help scale up workloads to very large computing systems. The techniques apply to NNs, DNNs and GANs. This talk also emphasized the impact of data movement associated with these large workloads and presented some techniques to address the related issues.

Micheal Simpson (NOAA) described work related to **climate impacts**, specifically technology to provide accurate, rapid **forecasts of precipitation** using Radar and other sensor inputs with examples in Taiwan and North America. Improvements to existing techniques in areas of low radar coverage were presented based on CNNs/LSTMs.

Pete Warden (Google) gave an overview of the new opportunities presented by using ML with edge devices (programmed with, for example, TensorFlow-lite) based on the existence and deployment of large numbers of cheap, low-energy edge devices with processors and sensors (including cameras, etc.). These allow the gathering of large amounts of (local) data of different forms which can be efficiently processed locally with ML techniques before being returned and stored centrally. Such systems can, for example, make local human-like judgements which can then be reported (cheaply and efficiently) rather than returning large amounts of raw data for processing.

Phil Ridley (Arm) reported on Arm specific support for ML at each level of their hardware and software stack. This ranged from support for the Open Container Initiative, through ML language and library support on their suite of devices, including specialised neural processors, to instruction-level support on current and emerging devices (e.g., their up-coming Zeus processor with half-precision support).

Jan Ackmann (Oxford University) described ML techniques (based on NNs) to find better and faster preconditioners for the linear solvers used in geophysical flows. Preconditioners represent, in fact, computationally expensive components in linear solvers and ML approaches have been investigated to replace them.

Theo McCaie (MetOffice Informatics Lab) discussed next-generation data platforms to support more efficient data analytic activities. The talk proposed the idea that the community should aim to provide **analysis-ready datasets** and discussed initiatives such as STAC (Spatio-temporal Asset Catalogue) and the work of the Pangeo community as examples of tools and standard-based work in this direction.

Torsten Kurth (NVIDIA) described NVIDIA’s Deep Learning technology being developed in the context of the **reduction of model bias in ECMWF’s IFS** model. In particular, a DL approach for offline bias correction based on satellite temperature retrievals from Radio Occultation (RO)

measurements was presented. The model bias was diagnosed within ECMWF's 4DVar data assimilation framework.

5. References (Bibliography)

Link to the event web page with the agenda and the presentations:

<https://portal.enes.org/community/announcements/events/joint-is-enes3-esiwace2-virtual-workshop-on-new-opportunities-for-ml-and-ai-in-weather-and-climate-modelling>

Link to the video playlist on YouTube to access the recordings:

<https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLFvev1W5vG7NP2xSRRorQabHWKKwJqw54>

Deliverable D2.6: Aloisio, Giovanni, Riley, Graham, Fiore, Sandro, & Osuna, Carlos. (2020). First white paper on community guidelines on the use, value and applicability of emerging technologies in climate and weather applications. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4001484>

6. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

The workshop was organized as a joint workshop with the IS-ENES3 project in March 2021, slightly delayed with respect to the original target of Month 24 due to COVID-19 in the hope of being able to hold a physical event. In the end, due to ongoing COVID-19 situation, it was held as virtual event.

7. How this deliverable contributes to the European strategies for HPC

The workshop brought together climate scientists and experts from academia, research centers and industry with the aim of sharing knowledge and experiences for identifying new opportunities in the fields of ML/AI for Weather and Climate Modelling. The talks and discussions given during the event contribute to raising the awareness of such novel opportunities within the European Weather and Climate community. ML/AI can, in fact, represent innovative technologies with the potential (i) for improving specific components of the weather and climate models (in terms of quality and speed), as well as the related data management aspects, and (ii) for increased adoption of accelerator-based HPC technologies (e.g., GPUs, NPUs, FPGAs) within the ESM community.

8. Sustainability

The workshop was organized jointly with IS-ENES3, further strengthening the link with this project; as previously mentioned, aspects related to this workshop are also described and explored in IS-ENES3 milestone MS16 and deliverable D4.5.

Moreover, this workshop lies within the path of workshops organized and supported by ESiWACE2, targeting innovative technologies for weather and climate change, and it follows other events in the frame of WP2 such as the “*ESiWACE2 Virtual Workshop on Emerging Technologies for Weather and Climate*” (June 30, 2020), reported in the deliverable D2.6 white paper. A second workshop on

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emerging technologies is planned during the final year of the ESiWACE2 project (2022) and will provide an updated view on these technologies.

The experience built through the organization of previous virtual events in the frame of the project was also useful in the organization of this online event.

Finally, the virtual location of the workshop allowed the participation of a large audience reaching several countries. The workshop had a diverse audience in terms of both the background and gender of the speakers and participants with scientists and experts from academia, weather and climate centres and a range of commercial organizations.

9. Dissemination, Engagement and Uptake of Results

9.1 Target audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

x	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This report is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience:

The event was widely announced to the target audience and well received as it was attended by a large number of participants (more than 200). The slides of most presentations have been published on the event website and made available to the participants. Presentations were also recorded and are available on YouTube to further reach out to the interested audience beyond workshop participants. All the slides and related links are publicly available on the event website: <https://portal.enes.org/community/announcements/events/joint-is-enes3-esiwace2-virtual-workshop-on-new-opportunities-for-ml-and-ai-in-weather-and-climate-modelling>.

9.2 Record of dissemination/engagement activities linked to this deliverable

Type of dissemination and communication activities	Details	Date and location of the event	Type of audience	Zenodo Link	Estimated number of persons reached
Organisation of a workshop	Joint IS-ENES3/ESiWACE2 Virtual Workshop on New	16-18 March 2021	Scientific community and industry	https://portal.enes.org/community/announcements/events/joint-is-enes3-esiwace2-	287

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	Opportunities for ML/AI in Weather and Climate Modelling			virtual-workshop-on-new-opportunities-for-ml-and-ai-in-weather-and-climate-modelling	
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9.3 Publications in preparation OR submitted

Please note that we are committed to Open Access: either go for the golden OA or for the green OA.

In preparation OR submitted?	Title	All authors	Title of the periodical or the series	Is/Will <i>open access</i> be provided to this publication?

9.4 Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable

N.A

10. Annex 1: Workshop Agenda

Virtual Workshop on New Opportunities in ML/AI for Weather and Climate - Agenda

March 16-18, 2021, 15:00 - 18:30 CET (Central European Time)

Connection details: TBA

14:45-15:00	<i>VC Available for test</i>	
15:00-15:05	Welcome	G. D. Riley, G. Aloisio
15:05-18:30	Session 1 – Views from Domain Science, Tuesday, 16th March	Chair: Marlene Kretschmer
Q&A: TBA		
15:05-15:45	New approaches based on ML for a range of climate prediction problems	Emily Shuckburgh (U. Cambridge)
15:45-16:05	Philosophy and Targeted Applications of ML/AI Techniques for Climate Risk Analytics at Jupiter	Luke Madaus & Steve Sain (Jupiter Intel.)
16:05-16:25	The optimization dichotomy: Why is it so hard to improve climate models with machine learning.	Stephan Rasp (ClimateAI)
16:25-16:45	<i>Break</i>	
16:45-17:05	Improving convection parameterizations with a library of large-eddy simulations	Zhaoyi Shen (Caltech)
17:05-17:25	Stochastic Super-Resolution for Convective Regimes using Gaussian Random Fields	Rachel Prudden (Met Office Inf. Lab)
17:25-17:45	Subseasonal Forecasts of Opportunity Identified by an Explainable Neural Network	Kirsten Mayer (CSU)

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17:45-18:05	Using transfer learning and backscattering analysis to build stable, generalizable data-driven subgrid-scale models: A 2D turbulence test case	Pedram Hassanzadeh (U. Rice)
18:05-18:30	Panel Session	
18:30	<i>End</i>	

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15:00-18:30	Session 2 – ML/AI Software technologies, Wednesday, 17th March	Chair: Caroline Arnold
Q&A: TBA		
15:00-15:40	Stochastic machine learning for atmospheric fields with generative adversarial networks	Jussi Leinonen (MeteoSwiss)
15:40-16:00	Causal discovery in time series with unobserved confounders	Andreas Gerhardus (DLR Jena)
16:00-16:20	Estimating stochastic closures using sparsity-promoting ensemble Kalman inversion	Jinlong Wu (Caltech)
16:20-16:40	<i>Break</i>	
16:40-17:00	Deep Learning on the sphere for weather/climate applications	Gionata Ghiggi and Michaël Defferrard (EPFL)
17:00-17:20	Deep learning-based remote sensing for infrastructure damage assessment	Thomas Chen (AMSE)
17:20-17:40	Leveraging physics information in neural networks for fluid flow problems	Akshay Subramaniam (NVIDIA)
17:40-18:00	Sub-seasonal forecasting with a large ensemble of deep-learning weather prediction models	Jonathan Weyn (U. of Washington)
18:00-18:30	Panel Session	
18:30	<i>End</i>	

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15:00-18:30	Session 3 – High performance, Infrastructure and Big data challenges, Thursday, 18th March	Chair: Carlos Gomez Gonzalez
Q&A: TBA		
15:00-15:40	Scaling Up Deep Learning Workloads - A Data-Centric View	Tal Ben-Nun (ETHZ)
15:40-16:00	Radar QPE and Machine Learning	Micheal Simpson (NOAA)
16:00-16:20	Using ML at the Edge to Improve Data Gathering	Pete Warden (Google)
16:20-16:40	<i>Break</i>	
16:40-17:00	An Overview of ML and AI on Arm Based HPC Systems for Weather and Climate Applications	Phil Ridley (Arm)
17:00-17:20	Machine-Learned Preconditioners for Linear Solvers in Geophysical Fluid Flows	Jan Ackmann (U. Oxford)
17:20-17:40	You do you. How next-gen data platforms can stop weather and climate scientists from being software engineers and other perversions	Theo McCaie (MO Informatics Lab)
17:40-18:00	3D bias correction with deep learning in the Integrated Forecasting System	Thorsten Kurth (NVIDIA)
18:00-18:30	Panel Session	
18:30	<i>Wrap-up and End</i>	

Program Committee

Graham Riley, Giovanni Aloisio, Jean-Claude Andre, Caroline Arnold, V. Balaji, Peter Dueben, Marlene Kretschmer, Carlos Gomez Gonzalez, Donatello Elia

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